

Fast electromembrane extraction of illicit drugs from meconium

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ABSTRACT

Neonatal meconium is a widely accepted biological matrix for assessing prenatal exposure to drugs of abuse. Its complex and heterogeneous nature, along with typically low target analyte concentrations, possess significant analytical challenges. This study reports the first application of electromembrane extraction for processing meconium, providing a protocol for isolating amphetamines and synthetic cathinones from only 50 mg of sample. Extraction parameters, including the supported liquid membrane composition, donor solution composition and pH, voltage, and shaking intensity, were systematically optimized. Electromembrane extraction followed by UHPLC-MS/MS assay was validated, achieving low limits of quantification ($2 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), along with consistent recoveries (55–65%) and high reproducibility (RSD < 5%) for all analytes. The method was successfully applied to a real neonatal meconium sample, in which amphetamine and methamphetamine were found. Several analytical performance parameters were compared with those of the previously published LC-MS based assays. The environmental impact was assessed using the Analytical Greenness Metric for Sample Preparation, showing that electromembrane extraction substantially reduces organic solvent and plastic consumption, operator exposure and preparation time, compared with conventional methods such as solid-phase extraction and salting-out assisted liquid–liquid extraction. Overall, electromembrane extraction provides a robust, high-throughput, and sustainable strategy for neonatal toxicology screening, with potential for broader adoption in clinical and forensic laboratories.

1. Introduction

Prenatal exposure to amphetamines and synthetic cathinones, can significantly disrupt fetal brain development [1]. Newborns exposed to these stimulants often exhibit neurological abnormalities, e.g. poor motor performance, abnormal electroencephalographic patterns, and high stress reactivity, soon after birth [2]. Animal and clinical studies suggest these drugs alter neurotransmitter systems (dopamine, serotonin) in the developing brain [3]. Prenatal exposure to amphetamines and synthetic cathinones can lead to long-term cognitive deficits in children [4]. These effects often persist and may include problems with

memory, information processing, and academic performance, emphasizing a need for early intervention and monitoring [2].

Meconium is regarded as the gold standard for detecting prenatal drug exposure *in utero* [5]. Fetal meconium formation starts around the beginning of the second trimester, roughly at 11–12 weeks of gestation. Meconium analysis reflects approximately the last 20 weeks of gestation, providing a broad window for detection of prenatal drug exposure [6,7]. Screening for drugs of abuse often begins with immunoassay tests (e.g. ELISA) on meconium extracts for a rapid, broad detection of drug classes. However, due to the risk of false positives and negatives, confirmatory chromatographic assay is required [6]. The direct

Abbreviations: 4-FMC, Flephedrone; 4-MEC, 4-Methylethcathinone; AGREEprep, Analytical GREENness metric for sample preparation; α -PHP, α -pyrrolidino-hexanophenone; α -PVP, α -pyrrolidinovalerophenone; AMP, Amphetamine; MAMP, Methamphetamine; MDMA, 3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine; MDPV, Methylenedioxypyrovalerone; MEPH, Mephedrone; METH, Methcathinone.

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Fig. 1. Chemical structures and selected physicochemical properties of the target analytes and their deuterated internal standards. Physicochemical properties were obtained from PubChem database or calculated using the ChemDraw software (version 22.2.0).

chromatographic analysis of meconium is challenging, particularly due to its highly complex, viscous and tar-like matrix nature. Moreover, it is non-homogeneous material that usually contains very low analyte concentrations, making thorough extraction and cleanup essential [5,6].

Solid-phase extraction (SPE) is a widely employed technique in forensic analysis for purification of complex samples. Notably, SPE represents the predominant method for the isolation of drugs from meconium. Although this technique typically yields clean extracts, it is often time-consuming, labor-intensive and costly. The standard SPE protocol for meconium processing includes the following steps: sample homogenization, preliminary liquid extraction, multiple washing and eluting steps on SPE columns and final extract evaporation and reconstitution [5,8,9]. Other conventional techniques have also been utilized for drugs isolation from meconium, including liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) [10], salting-out assisted liquid-liquid extraction (SALLE) [11], and supported liquid extraction (SLE) [12]. Each of these techniques has its own limitations, such as extensive sample handling, large solvent consumption, and relatively long processing time. Although miniaturized formats such as disposable pipette extraction have been introduced and allow for reducing sample volume and simplifying the workflow [13], their application in meconium processing remains limited. The current trend in sample preparation clearly favors miniaturized and environmentally friendly approaches that reduce organic solvents consumption, minimize waste generation, and are suitable for samples of low amounts [14]. These demands emphasize the need for developing of

novel extraction strategies.

Electromembrane extraction (EME) is a modern extraction technique combining principles of liquid-phase microextraction with electrophoresis. By applying a direct current voltage, charged analytes migrate from an aqueous donor phase through a few microliters of a water-immiscible organic solvent immobilized in a porous membrane (supported liquid membrane, SLM) into an aqueous acceptor solution [15]. EME provides efficient sample clean-up and effective isolation of target analytes in a single step, even when applied to complex biological matrices. Furthermore, the technique is inherently miniaturized, requires only microliter volumes of an organic solvent, and thereby aligns with current principles of green and sustainable sample preparation [16]. In addition, the implementation of EME in a 96-well format represents a promising platform for high-throughput processing of small weight biological samples, further underlining its applicability within sustainable modern bioanalytical workflows [17]. Although EME has been successfully applied for the extraction of drugs of abuse from whole blood, plasma, urine, micro pulverized hair, and breast milk [18–22], its application to meconium has not yet been reported. This gap is particularly noteworthy given the complex and heterogeneous nature of meconium, which is rich in endogenous components known to induce pronounced matrix effects in LC-MS-based assays, despite the demonstrated clean-up capability of EME in other challenging biological matrices [18,20,23]. Introducing EME into meconium analysis therefore represents more than a simple extension of an established method; it

addresses a significant methodological challenge associated with the processing of complex neonatal samples that has not yet been systematically resolved.

The aim of this study was to optimize the EME conditions for the isolation of amphetamine-type stimulants from meconium and to evaluate the applicability of the method to a real meconium sample. This research therefore opens the door to further employment of this innovative technique in neonatal toxicology.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Amphetamine (AMP), methamphetamine (MAMP), 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA), along with their deuterated internal standards (AMP-d5, MAMP-d11, and MDMA-d5), were obtained as 1 mg·mL⁻¹ methanolic solutions from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Methyone (METH), 3,4-methylenedioxypyrovalerone (MDPV), mephedrone (MEPH), α -pyrrolidinovalerophenone (α -PVP), flephedrone (4-FMC), buphedrone, α -pyrrolidinohexanophenone (α -PHP), ethylone, 4-methylethcathinone (4-MEC), pentadron, and pentylone were obtained as solid substances from Alfarma (Prague, Czech Republic). MDPV-d8 was synthesized at the Forensic Laboratory of Biologically Active Compounds (University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic) and characterized using nuclear magnetic resonance, infrared spectroscopy, and mass spectrometry. The structures of the analyzed compounds and internal standards are shown in Fig. 1.

Acetonitrile, methanol, and formic acid (98–100 %) (all LC-MS grade), bis(2-ethylhexyl) phosphite (DEHPi), 2-nitrophenyl octyl ether (NPOE), 2-nitrophenyl pentyl ether (NPPE), 1-ethyl-2-nitrobenzen (ENB), 1-undecanol, levomenthol, camphor, coumarin and thymol were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Milli-Q water was obtained from Millipore purification system (Merck-Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany).

2.2. Preparation of stock, working solutions and buffers

The stock solutions of the analytes and internal standards (ISs; 500 μ g mL⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving a relevant amount of the substance in methanol and stored at -20 °C until use. Working solutions of the analytes (0.025–20 μ g·mL⁻¹) and ISs (5 μ g·mL⁻¹) were prepared by the appropriate dilution of the stock solution with the same solvent and used within three months, when stored at -20 °C. The formic acid solutions (0.09%, 1% and 5% with corresponding pH values of pH 2.7, 2.5 and 2.2, respectively) were prepared by diluting appropriate volumes of formic acid in Milli-Q water. Deep eutectic solvents were prepared by weighing the individual components in the following molar ratios: camphor:levomenthol (1:1 mol/mol, CM11), coumarin:thymol (1:1, mol/mol, CT11), coumarin:thymol (2:1, mol/mol, CT21), and coumarin:thymol (1:2, mol/mol, CT12). The resulting mixtures were then heated in an oven (HS Chirana, Prague, Czech Republic) at 80 °C for 15 min.

2.3. Meconium samples

Pooled analyte-free meconium samples obtained from voluntary donors ($n = 5$) were obtained as residual clinical material originally collected for routine healthcare purposes, dedicated for disposal, and provided in fully anonymized by the Department of Clinical Biochemistry and Diagnostics, University Hospital and Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové (Czech Republic). The material was used for the development of the extraction as well as for method validation. A real meconium sample, originally collected for clinical purposes by the Regional Hospital Příbram (Czech Republic) and subsequently designated for disposal, was provided to our laboratory. For the purposes of this study, the sample was fully anonymized. All meconium samples

were stored at -20 °C until analysis.

2.4. Sample treatment

The EME protocol for meconium processing was adapted from a previously described method for isolation of amphetamines and synthetic cathinones from breast milk [18]. Briefly, the EME was carried out using a laboratory built 96-well format device composed of a custom-made stainless-steel donor plate and an aluminum lid equipped with electrode rods for each well, and a 96-well filter plate with a PVDF membrane (0.45 μ m pore size, Millipore Ltd., Carrigtwohill, Ireland). Three μ L of organic solvent were added to the outer part of each PVDF membrane. Subsequently, the donor plate, with a sample, was securely sealed with the acceptor plate, and each acceptor well was filled with 100 μ L of the acceptor solution. Finally, the setup was completed by placing the top electrode lid over the system. During the extraction, the plate was agitated at 1050 rpm using a Vibramax 100 (Heidolph, Kelheim, Germany). A Model ES 0300-0.45 (Delta Elektronika BV, Zierikzee, The Netherlands) was used as the power supply, and the current was monitored by a digital multimeter (Volcraft VC 830, Conrade Electronics, Hirschau, Germany). At the end of the extraction, the acceptor solution was collected and analyzed by UHPLC-MS/MS.

Firstly, the impact of meconium on recovery was evaluated using selected amphetamines (AMF, MAMF, and MDMA, all 20 ng·g⁻¹), and varying amounts of meconium (20–55 mg). Then the optimal amount of meconium was weighed directly into the donor plate and used for further optimization of the extraction protocol with all analytes (AMP, MAMP, MDMA, METH, MDPV, MEPH, α -PVP, 4-FMC, buphedrone, α -PHP, ethylone, 4-MEC, pentadron, and pentylone). The impact of following experimental parameters on process efficiency, recovery, or matrix effects was examined. Different acceptor (0.09 %, 1 % and 5 % formic acid) and donor (0.09 %, 1 %, 5 % formic acid, and 1 % formic acid with 10 % of MeOH) solutions and deep eutectic solvents (CM11, CT11, CT21, and CT12) used for the SLM were tested using matrix-free aqueous samples (10 ng·mL⁻¹, $n = 3$ for all conditions). Subsequently, various organic solvents used for the SLM (NPOE:DEHPi 1:1, w/w; NPPE:DEHPi 1:1, w/w and ENB:1-undecanol 1:1, w/w), applied voltage (5–35 V), and extraction time (20–45 min) were evaluated using spiked meconium samples (20 ng·g⁻¹, $n = 3$ for recovery and $n = 2$ for matrix effects). After each run, the donor plate and top electrode lid were properly washed with Milli-Q water and ethanol to eliminate potential cross-contamination.

Last evaluated parameter was the effect of meconium homogenization prior to extraction. Fifty milligrams of analyte-free meconium were weighed into Eppendorf tubes ($n = 3$), and spiked with target analytes and ISs (20 ng·g⁻¹). The samples were then mixed with 180 μ L of 1 % formic acid and vortexed briefly prior to homogenization. Two different homogenization techniques were evaluated. (1) Ultrasonic homogenization: the samples underwent two cycles of 10-minute sonication in a water-cooled ultrasonic bath (maintained at 10 °C), each followed by 10 seconds of vortex mixing. (2) Mechanical homogenization was performed using an Ultra-Turrax homogenizer (T 10 basic, IKA-Werke GmbH & Co. KG, Staufen, Germany) for 50 seconds, followed by vortex mixing. All homogenized meconium samples were then transferred into the donor wells and extracted under the optimized EME conditions. Extraction recoveries and matrix effects were subsequently compared for both homogenization approaches as well as for a non-homogenized control sample.

Process efficiency, recovery and matrix effects were calculated based on equations presented in the Electronic Supplementary materials (part 1.1).

2.5. UHPLC-MS/MS method

The analysis was performed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity II liquid chromatography system coupled with a 6470 Triple Quadrupole LC/MS,

Fig. 2. Optimization of composition of donor and acceptor solutions. Recoveries of the analytes obtained after twenty-minute extraction from spiked aqueous samples ($10 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) using NPOE:DEHPi (1:1 v/v) as SLM. Recoveries are presented as a mean \pm SD ($n = 4$).

equipped with a Jet Stream Electrospray ion source and controlled by Mass Hunter software (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The Luna Omega Polar C18 column ($100 \times 2.1 \text{ mm}$, $1.6 \mu\text{m}$) protected with the same type of guard column, both from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA), maintained at $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, was used for chromatographic separation.

Formic acid 0.1 % and acetonitrile were used as mobile phase A and B, respectively, and the flow rate of the mobile phase was 0.3 mL min^{-1} . The following gradient was used: 0.0–13.0 (2–30 % B), 13.1–15.0 (100 % B), 15.1–17.0 (2 % B). The autosampler was maintained at $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the injection volume was $3 \mu\text{L}$.

The mass spectrometer, working in positive ion mode, was tuned automatically. The following settings were used: gas temperature $330 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, gas flow 6 L min^{-1} , sheath gas temperature $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, sheath gas flow 11 L min^{-1} , nebulizer 25 psi, capillary voltage 3000 V, and nozzle voltage 0 V. Quantification was performed in selected reaction monitoring mode with a dwell time of 20 ms. The transitions and collision energies of analytes and isotopically labeled ISs are summarized in **Table S1**. For representative chromatograms at LLOQ level see **Figure S1**.

2.6. Method validation

The EME followed by UHPLC-MS/MS was validated for the quantitative analysis of AMP, MAMP, MDMA, and 11 synthetic cathinones (METH, MDPV, MEPH, α -PVP, 4-FMC, buphedrone, α -PHP, ethylone, 4-

MEC, pentedrone, and pentylone) in meconium. Validation parameters, including selectivity, linearity, accuracy, precision, recovery, matrix effects (ME), and carry-over were assessed in accordance with the European Medicines Agency (EMA) guideline [24].

Selectivity was verified using analyte-free meconium samples ($n = 5$), by monitoring potential interferences at the retention times of target analytes and their internal standards. A calibration curve (seven concentration levels) was constructed using spiked meconium samples with the analytes ranging from 2 to $400 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Accuracy and precision were evaluated at four concentration levels (lower limit of quantification (LLOQ), low, medium, and upper limit of quantification (ULOQ), both within- and between-run. These parameters were expressed as mean percentage of the nominal concentration (accuracy) and as relative standard deviations (RSDs; precision) based on six individually prepared quality control (QC) meconium samples.

Extraction recovery ($n = 6$) and matrix effects ($n = 5$) were evaluated at low and high concentration levels using calculations specified in Electronic Supplementary Information (part 1.1). Carry-over was evaluated by monitoring signals at the retention times of the target analytes and their internal standards in analyte-free meconium samples ($n = 5$) injected immediately after the ULOQ sample.

3. Results and discussion

Electromembrane extraction has been increasingly applied for the

Fig. 3. Optimization of SLM composition – DES-based SLMs. Recoveries of the analytes obtained after twenty-minute extraction from aqueous samples ($10 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) using 0.09 % formic acid as both the donor and the acceptor solutions. CM11 (camphor:levomenthol 1:1, mol/mol), CT11 (coumarin:thymol 1:1, mol/mol), CT12 (coumarin:thymol 1:2, mol/mol), and CT21 (coumarin:thymol 2:1, mol/mol). Recoveries are presented as a mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

Fig. 4. Optimization of SLM composition. Recoveries (A) and matrix effects (B) of the analytes obtained after twenty-minute extraction from a spiked meconium sample ($20 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) using 1 % formic acid as both the donor and the acceptor solutions. Recoveries are presented as a mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Matrix effects were calculated from a single experiment.

effective treatment of a wide variety of complex biological matrices [20, 23,25]. In the context of forensic toxicology, EME has been successfully used for the extraction of stimulants from undiluted blood, cathinones from plasma, amphetamines and cathinones from human breast milk, and abused drugs from micropulverized hair [18–20,22]. This study builds upon previous research [18] and investigates whether EME can serve as an effective alternative for extracting stimulants from meconium.

3.1. Optimization of EME procedure

In preliminary experiments, we applied EME conditions previously developed for the processing of breast milk to isolate three selected analytes (AMF, MAMF, and MDMA) from meconium. Meconium samples of various weights (from 20 to 55 mg) were extracted to test the applicability of the conditions for this matrix and to select the optimal sample weight [18]. Based on the well volume and the observed decline in process efficiency at higher meconium amounts – likely due to saturation of the sample-SLM interface, which hindered analyte transfer – we selected 50 mg for all further experiments. In parallel, the volume of the donor solution was optimized with respect to the well capacity, and 180 μL was found to be optimal. As demonstrated in **Figure S2**, the recoveries from meconium were significantly lower than those from breast milk, suggesting that the EME conditions developed for extractions of amphetamines from breast milk were not optimal for isolation of AMF, MAMP, and MDMA from meconium. This is likely due to the complex, adsorptive nature of meconium and this underlines the need for systematic optimization of the EME parameters specifically for this matrix. The following experiments utilized all analytes in this study,

focused on the impact of donor and acceptor composition on the extraction recovery. Different concentrations of FA were tested (0.09–5 %) and results indicated that 1 % FA provided the highest recoveries (**Fig. 2**).

As the next step in the optimization process, we focused on selecting a suitable organic solvent for SLM, which is a key component of the EME system [26]. In pursuit of a greener extraction, we initially explored hydrophobic deep eutectic solvents (DES) as an alternative. However, even using simple aqueous donor solutions, all DES yielded insufficient recoveries, especially for MDPV, α -PVP, and α -PHP (**Fig. 3**). Therefore, we tested and compared three conventional binary solvents SLM of varying polarity. First, we replaced NPOE with NPPE, whose intrinsic hydrophobicity is significantly lower [27], and this should improve partitioning of the analytes with $\log P < 2$ [28]. The ENB:1-undecanol mixture, on the other hand, combines an aromatic nitrobenzene – known for high dipolarity/polarizability and hydrogen-bond basicity [26] – with a long-chain alcohol that can further modulate polarity and viscosity, thereby reducing SLM fouling by matrix macromolecules [29]. Such binary SLM systems have also been shown to improve the extraction of synthetic cathinones from urine [30].

Upon testing these SLMs, all three binary solvent mixtures provided close recovery (**Fig. 4**) but originally used NPOE:DEHPi demonstrated greater variability (high RSDs), possibly due to instability of the solvent in the membrane or interactions with the matrix. Moreover, extractions using this solvent mixture exhibited higher matrix effects. The other two mixtures provided high reproducibility with significantly reduced matrix effects for most of the analytes, with the exception of MDPV, where significant suppression was observed with NPPE:DEHPi mixture. Based on these results, ENB:1-undecanol showed the best overall performance

Fig. 5. Optimization of extraction time. Recoveries (A) and matrix effects (B) obtained after extraction of the analytes from a spiked meconium sample ($20 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) using 1 % formic acid as both the donor and the acceptor solutions and ENB:1-undecanol (1:1, w/w) as SLM. Recoveries are presented as a mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Matrix effects were calculated from a single experiment.

(Fig. 4). This is consistent with previous findings that nitrobenzene derivatives were particularly effective SLM solvents for the extraction of basic drugs [26]. By combining ENB with 1-undecanol, the membrane likely achieves an optimal balance of polarity and viscosity, facilitating the transport of analytes while impeding the passage of large matrix components.

Using the ENB:1-undecanol mixture as an organic solvent and 1 % formic acid in both the donor and the acceptor phase, the effect of extraction time was examined. Triplicate extractions were performed for 20, 35, and 45 min and the recovery and matrix effects were compared. Extending the extraction time beyond 20 min did not result in an increase in analyte recovery (Fig. 5a). In contrast, the longer extractions (35 and 45 min) led to visibly higher matrix effects (Fig. 5b). Therefore, 20 min was considered sufficient and optimal for EME of meconium, as it minimizes the analysis time and limits the co-extraction of undesired matrix constituents.

Given the solid and heterogeneous nature of meconium, analytes are usually released from the matrix by thorough grinding or sonication. Therefore, we evaluated whether additional sample homogenization could further improve extraction efficiency. We tested two approaches on spiked meconium (50 mg) prior to EME: (1) ultrasonic agitation (bath sonication) combined with vortex mixing, and (2) mechanical rotor-stator homogenization (Ultra-Turrax). The homogenized samples were then subjected to EME and the recovery and matrix effects were compared with vortex-mixed (non-homogenized) samples as controls. The results showed no improvement of recoveries (Fig. 6a). In contrast, homogenization consistently led to increased matrix effects, presumably due to dispersion of fine matrix particulates in the donor phase, which were ultimately transferred into the extract (Fig. 6b). These findings

corroborate recent research demonstrating that EME can effectively isolate drugs directly from pulverized or minimally treated tissues without the need for extensive homogenization, with only minimal matrix effects [23]. In our case, the standard practice of briefly pipette tip-mixing the meconium with acid in the well (to create a uniform slurry) was sufficient.

The optimized extraction was performed using a voltage of 20–25 V, which ensured smooth operation without gas generation or SLM leakage.

3.2. Method validation

The following EME protocol was found to be optimal for isolation of amphetamines and synthetic cathinones from 50 mg of meconium: a supported liquid membrane composed of 3 μL of ENB:1-undecanol (1:1, w/w), 1 % formic acid in donor and acceptor solution (180 and 100 μL , respectively), extraction time of 20 min, agitation at 1050 rpm, and stepwise voltage application (15 V increased to 30 V after 1 minute). The EME procedure followed by LC-MS/MS assay was validated for the determination of amphetamines and synthetic cathinones in meconium within a concentration range 2–400 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. The LLOQ was established according to the response of the least sensitive analyte to ensure consistent calibration levels for all analytes throughout the validation process. The main validation parameters are summarized in Table 1, and all complied with the EME guideline recommendations [31]. Examples of calibration curves are presented in Figure S3. Carry-over evaluation showed that the highest signal detected in the analyte-free meconium sample injected after the ULOQ meconium sample corresponded to 10 % of the LLOQ (for MAMP) and ≤ 6.5 % of the LLOQ for the remaining

Fig. 6. Impact of homogenization step prior EME. Recoveries (A) and matrix effects (B) obtained after twenty-minute extraction of the analytes from a spiked meconium sample ($20 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) using 1 % formic acid as both the donor and the acceptor solutions and ENB:1-udecanol (1:1, w/w) as SLM with and without an additional homogenization step prior to the extraction. Data are presented as a mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

target analytes. For internal standards, the observed signal was below 0.3 % of the LLOQ. This clearly proved the acceptable carry-over. Matrix effects evaluated by post-extraction addition experiments ranged from 92 to 101 % and 93–101 % for the absolute and IS-normalized matrix factors, respectively. Values close to 100 % indicate negligible matrix-induced signal suppression or enhancement for all analytes. According to the EMA guideline, acceptable matrix effect is defined as a deviation in accuracy within ± 15 % of the nominal value (i.e. 100 %) and with a maximum RSD of 15 %, which was fulfilled (Table 1). The recoveries of all analytes were > 52 %, exceeding the generally accepted threshold for EME-based assays (> 40 %) to ensure reliable quantitative performance [20,32].

3.3. Proof-of-concept: real sample analysis

In the analyzed clinical sample set, a single authentic meconium specimen was included as a proof-of-concept sample to evaluate method performance under real-world conditions. The meconium specimen was analyzed as received (without an additional homogenization step) using EME on three independent 50 mg aliquots. The clinical sample was positive for AMF and MAMF, with concentrations of $175 \pm 20.9 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and $368 \pm 44.9 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, respectively. Given the known heterogeneity and uneven deposition of substances in meconium, the observed between-aliquot variability is consistent with expected subsampling variability from small analytical portions rather than systematic analytical bias [33]. Both analytes were quantified well above the method LLOQ ($2 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), supporting reliable quantification in this proof-of-concept sample. For comparison, studies such as López-Rabuñal et al. (2019) and Nemeškalová et al. (2019) report

median meconium concentrations in exposed newborns around $285\text{--}613 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for AMF and $1455\text{--}3514 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for MAMF, with extremes exceeding $10,000 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ in severe cases [8,11], whereas lower concentrations ($\sim 5\text{--}15 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) were also reported in confirmed third-trimester exposure [34]. In this context, the concentrations observed here fall within the broad range described in the literature. Contrary, it was observed that the determined concentrations of illicit drugs in meconium may vary depending on the selected preanalytical procedures, including sample collection and storage conditions, which complicates direct comparison between studies. However, a limited dataset from a clinical perspective, our microscale EME demonstrates that it is capable of detecting exposure levels in neonatal matrices. Such an approach facilitates practical implementation through reduced sample requirements while maintaining analytical reliability, thereby supporting improved pharmacological and toxicological assessment in neonatal settings [35].

3.4. Comparison with previously published methods

3.4.1. The analytical performance

The analytical performance of the developed method for determining amphetamines and synthetic cathinones in meconium was compared with other LC-MS-based methods reported in the literature. Key validation parameters, including sample consumption, LLOQ, recovery or process efficiency, and matrix effects, were addressed. Only studies reporting at least three analytes overlapping with those in this work and providing sufficient validation data were included (Table 2). For clarity, the values reported for the EME method in Table 2 were obtained during method optimization using homogenized matrix ($n = 3$). As such, these

Table 1

Validation parameters for EME followed by UHPLC-MS/MS assay of amphetamines and synthetic cathinones from meconium.

Analyte	Concentration (ng·g ⁻¹)	Intra-day		Inter-day		Recovery (% ± SD)	ME		ME IS normalized		Linearity (R ²)
		Accuracy (%)	Precision (RSD)	Accuracy (%)	Precision (RSD)		(%)	(RSD)	(%)	(RSD)	
AMP	2	99.9	10.4	101.0	7.3	60.3 ± 3.7	-	-	-	-	0.9936
	5	102.7	7.9	113.8	8.4	59.2 ± 5.5	94.9	5.5	98.9	6.1	
	100	93.5	7.6	95.9	10.1	60.6 ± 5.7	-	-	-	-	
	400	100.6	7.2	101.7	4.5	61.8 ± 4.8	99.6	1.8	96.7	7.1	
MAMP	2	104.4	6.2	101.7	5.5	62.0 ± 4.8	-	-	-	-	0.9929
	5	97.6	8.1	105.8	8.6	61.9 ± 6.0	97.0	4.2	98.9	6.3	
	100	93.0	6.9	95.3	12.1	61.5 ± 4.8	-	-	-	-	
	400	109.2	3.2	112.3	4.5	63.9 ± 3.3	100.5	1.5	96.1	8.7	
MDMA	2	97.9	8.6	101.9	7.6	60.8 ± 4.9	-	-	-	-	0.9940
	5	103.8	7.4	113.6	8.5	58.8 ± 3.8	95.2	4.2	95.5	5.2	
	100	96.9	7.5	99.8	8.5	59.9 ± 5.4	-	-	-	-	
	400	92.2	6.1	94.0	4.7	64.2 ± 2.7	100.2	1.7	95.4	7.9	
4-FMC	2	99.1	7.2	104.0	7.2	57.4 ± 4.3	-	-	-	-	0.9954
	5	100.1	6.6	109.6	8.3	55.7 ± 3.6	94.0	5.4	97.9	7.0	
	100	96.6	6.4	96.9	10.9	57.9 ± 5.1	-	-	-	-	
	400	104.7	4.4	105.2	5.3	62.7 ± 3.7	97.1	2.0	94.6	7.6	
MET	2	100.2	7.4	101.9	9.0	57.6 ± 4.6	-	-	-	-	0.9946
	5	98.7	6.4	110.0	8.0	54.6 ± 5.1	94.1	4.5	98.1	7.3	
	100	94.8	7.4	97.6	12.3	57.9 ± 5.2	-	-	-	-	
	400	104.1	3.6	107.9	4.5	62.7 ± 2.9	99.2	1.7	96.8	8.3	
Ethylone	2	99.4	7.1	105.5	7.9	61.0 ± 5.1	-	-	-	-	0.9930
	5	97.7	7.1	104.6	9.2	58.4 ± 3.9	95.0	4.8	99.1	7.0	
	100	94.4	7.4	98.0	12.5	59.3 ± 5.4	-	-	-	-	
	400	106.2	8.0	109.3	4.4	62.9 ± 4.3	100.3	1.9	97.8	8.6	
Buphedrone	2	99.0	6.3	102.3	9.0	60.4 ± 5.1	-	-	-	-	0.9955
	5	100.2	7.2	107.6	8.3	58.8 ± 3.8	96.6	3.9	100.8	7.0	
	100	96.7	6.9	99.5	10.9	61.8 ± 5.0	-	-	-	-	
	400	101.4	6.6	102.6	4.4	65.2 ± 4.0	101.1	1.5	98.6	8.2	
MEPH	2	94.8	7.2	96.5	7.9	61.3 ± 5.6	-	-	-	-	0.9926
	5	104.8	8.2	110.9	8.8	60.3 ± 3.6	92.3	6.0	92.6	6.1	
	100	96.4	8.8	98.0	8.2	61.6 ± 5.3	-	-	-	-	
	400	89.2	4.2	87.3	4.0	64.6 ± 4.0	96.6	2.3	94.0	7.4	
4-MEC	2	97.2	6.0	105.4	6.3	61.9 ± 5.1	-	-	-	-	0.9947
	5	102.3	8.0	111.4	8.2	61.0 ± 4.1	94.9	5.0	95.1	5.4	
	100	96.3	7.8	99.4	8.2	60.9 ± 5.7	-	-	-	-	
	400	93.6	5.2	97.5	4.4	62.8 ± 4.6	99.6	1.7	95.1	8.6	
Pentredone	2	92.8	6.8	104.3	6.5	62.3 ± 5.2	-	-	-	-	0.9935
	5	102.9	8.7	112.3	7.2	61.7 ± 3.9	96.0	5.1	96.3	6.3	
	100	95.9	8.6	99.1	7.7	61.8 ± 5.7	-	-	-	-	
	400	91.4	6.0	93.4	4.3	65.8 ± 2.5	98.2	1.5	94.1	9.0	
Pentylone	2	91.4	7.1	100.2	6.7	61.6 ± 5.7	-	-	-	-	0.9917
	5	104.3	10.3	113.3	9.3	60.4 ± 4.0	94.1	4.5	94.3	5.5	
	100	96.1	9.1	101.5	8.0	60.5 ± 4.9	-	-	-	-	
	400	90.2	4.8	90.9	4.2	66.8 ± 2.3	98.5	1.8	94.1	8.6	
α-PVP	2	99.8	9.1	100.1	8.5	58.0 ± 4.5	-	-	-	-	0.9940
	5	105.2	6.1	109.0	7.4	54.9 ± 3.5	95.1	5.1	99.0	5.6	
	100	98.3	7.1	98.0	8.1	54.8 ± 5.3	-	-	-	-	
	400	93.0	6.1	91.5	4.7	56.5 ± 3.3	98.3	2.7	97.4	7.6	
MDPV	2	96.5	6.5	100.6	9.0	54.8 ± 4.3	-	-	-	-	0.9946
	5	103.0	7.0	112.9	8.9	52.2 ± 4.6	92.7	7.5	96.5	7.5	
	100	97.5	7.5	100.2	9.1	53.8 ± 3.7	-	-	-	-	
	400	93.0	6.3	93.5	4.5	55.6 ± 3.6	95.5	4.4	95.3	9.2	
α-PHP	2	91.4	7.9	99.9	7.6	54.2 ± 4.3	-	-	-	-	0.9933
	5	103.2	9.5	108.6	8.1	53.7 ± 2.9	93.2	5.9	97.0	5.6	
	100	95.7	7.9	97.9	7.8	54.2 ± 3.9	-	-	-	-	
	400	91.7	6.6	89.7	4.5	56.3 ± 2.6	96.5	3.4	95.8	8.4	

ME – matrix effect, Linearity 2-400 ng·g⁻¹, weight: 1/x²

data are most comparable to recovery assessments performed on pooled samples in other studies. The purpose of this comparison is to contextualize the analytical performance of the developed EME method using validation data reported in relevant literature.

Although our EME provides slightly lower recoveries compared to some methods reported in the literature, this did not translate into reduced overall analytical performance of our EME-based assay. Recoveries above 52 % in our study ensured reliable quantification while maintaining excellent precision and LLOQ. Notably, our EME-based assay achieved the lowest LLOQs when normalized to the amount of sample used (Table 2). Specifically, EME achieved an LLOQ of 2 ng·g⁻¹

using only 0.05 g of meconium, whereas the most sensitive comparative method reported an LLOQ of 0.2 ng·g⁻¹ but required 2 g of sample [36]. These results were obtained without complex multi-step extraction procedures, including homogenization, or the use of several milliliters of organic solvents. Furthermore, the electro-driven selectivity of EME minimize co-extraction of matrix components, which is particularly advantageous for meconium—a material rich in endogenous compounds, representing a clear improvement compared to previously reported methods.

Table 2
Comparison of the developed method for determination of amphetamines and synthetic cathinones in meconium with other relevant LC-MS-based methods reported in the literature, including key analytical parameters and AGREeprep evaluation.

Extraction method	EME			SALLE						SPE								
Instrumentation Detector	UHPLC-MS/MS 6470 Triple Quadrupole (Agilent)			UHPLC-MS/MS QTRAP 6500+ (AB Sciex)			HPLC-MS/MS MDS Sciex API 3000 (Applied Biosystems)			HPLC-MS/MS Applied Biosystems/ Sciex 3200 Q TRAP (Applied Biosystems)			HPLC-MS/MS Quattro Micro™ API ESCI triple quadrupole (Waters)			HPLC-MS 1100 Series G1946D MS detector (Agilent)		
Sample amount	0.05 g			0.2 g			1 g			2 g			0.25 g			1 g		
Analytes	LLOQ (ng·g ⁻¹)	Rec (%)	ME (%)	LLOQ (ng·g ⁻¹)	Rec (%)	ME (%)	LLOQ (ng·g ⁻¹)	Rec (%)	ME (%)	LLOQ (ng·g ⁻¹)	Rec (%)	LLOQ (ng·g ⁻¹)	Rec (%)	ME (%)	LLOQ (ng·g ⁻¹)	Rec (%)	ME (%)	
AMP	2	66.4	94.9	10	58.2	98.3	12.5	73.7	85.2	0.5	48	-	-	-	5	60-70	> 90	
MAMP	2	69.1	97.0	10	64.7	97.7	12.5	71.3	91.3	0.2	63	-	-	-	5	80-90	> 90	
MDMA	2	67.3	95.2	10	69.9	91.4	12.5	71.2	99.3	0.3	63	-	-	-	4	80-90	> 90	
MET	2	65.6	94.1	10	65.8	98.3	-	-	-	-	-	1	70	59.8	-	-	-	
MEPH	2	68.1	92.3	10	62.9	92.2	-	-	-	-	-	1	63.7	60.9	-	-	-	
4-FMC	2	62.7	94.0	10	51.8	101.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
α-PVP	2	63.8	95.1	10	78.3	76.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
MDPV	2	60.9	92.7	10	94.3	60.2	-	-	-	-	-	1	85.9	36.2	-	-	-	

AGREeprep evaluation

References

[11]

[38]

[36]

[8]

[39]

Rec – recovery, ME – matrix effect, AGREeprep evaluation - the radar plots represent the relative performance of each method across ten AGREeprep criteria: (1) sample preparation placement, (2) hazardous reagents, (3) sustainability, (4) waste generated, (5) size economy, (6) throughput, (7) automation potential, (8) energy consumption, (9) post-preparation requirements, and (10) operator safety. Higher values indicate better performance. The overall AGREeprep score is shown in the center of each plot.

3.4.2. Sustainability aspects

In addition to the performance of the whole analytical procedure, EME was also evaluated using AGREEp prep metric [37], and it was compared with the traditional extraction methods (Table S2).

Conventional techniques generally perform less in terms of resource consumption and waste generation, as reflected in their AGREEp prep score assessment. The SALLE method for isolation of amphetamine-type stimulants from meconium uses several milliliters of organic solvent (e. g. acetonitrile) along with inorganic salts to induce phase separation [11]. Consequently, it generates significant waste, including salt-laden aqueous residues and organic solvents, which must be treated as hazardous waste.

The classical SPE protocols [8,36,38,39] require multiple steps (conditioning, loading, washing, and elution), each of which requires several milliliters of solvent. Prior to SPE, meconium is often homogenized in methanol, with or without the addition of acidic additives. This step further increases the volume of organic reagents consumed. Additionally, the use of disposable cartridges contributes to the material footprint of the analysis.

In contrast, EME greatly reduces the amount of hazardous organic solvents and consumable materials required per sample, thereby minimizing chemical waste at the source. Taken together, these features indicate that EME not only meets analytical needs but also provides tangible ecological benefits.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the first application of electromembrane extraction for the processing of neonatal meconium. The optimized EME protocol enabled the extraction of 14 illicit drugs (amphetamines and synthetic cathinones) from only 50 mg of meconium, achieving low LLOQs (2 ng·g⁻¹). All analytes exhibited recoveries exceeding 50 % along with good repeatability, as indicated by RSD values of <10 %. EME combined with LC-MS/MS assay was fully validated with all parameters meeting the required acceptance criteria. The practical applicability of the method was demonstrated through analysis of real samples obtained as a part of neonatal toxicology screening. Compared with conventional extraction techniques, our EME protocol brought benefits in terms of sample consumption, matrix effects, and overall sustainability. Owing to its reliance on only microliters of organic solvent and minimal aqueous volumes, the procedure markedly reduces hazardous reagent use, waste production, and operator exposure. Notably, the EME protocol required no additional homogenization step, thereby streamlining sample preparation and minimizing the risk of analyte loss or contamination. The high AGREEp prep scores further confirm its strong alignment with green analytical chemistry, underscoring its ecological benefits without compromising analytical performance. In summary, these findings position EME as a practical, robust, and environmentally responsible alternative to traditional meconium extraction methods, providing a solid foundation for its future implementation in high-throughput clinical and forensic applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hana Bavlovič Piskáčková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Radim Kučera:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Alžběta Nemeškalová:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Stig Pedersen-Bjergaard:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Petra Štěrbová-Kovářiková:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.greeac.2026.100337](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.greeac.2026.100337).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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